

TOWARDS IMPROVEMENT ON MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF BASALT FIBER/POLYLACTIC ACID COMPOSITES

B.S. Kim^{1*}, D. Kurniawan², H.Y. Lee², J.Y. Lim²

¹ Composite Materials Laboratory, Korea Institute of Materials Science, Changwon, Korea

² Mechanical, Robotics, and Energy Engineering Department, Dongguk University, Seoul, Korea

* Corresponding author (kbs@kims.re.kr)

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1 Introduction

Natural fiber composites are being developed to provide environmentally friendly yet economically justifiable structural and functional materials. For the constituents of these composites, bioplastics are often favored, and proposed, to be the matrix. Polylactid acid (PLA), being biodegradable and originated from vegetation, has ecofriendly image and fair physical properties to be the bio-based thermoplastic matrix of choice. As for the reinforcing constituent, basalt fiber (BF) which is made entirely of volcanic rock also has the natural notion. It has potentials of having high strength comparable to E-glass, stability at elevated temperature, fire resistance, and being inert and less harmful to human and environment. As added point, domestically, mountainous Korea potentially contains abundant resource for its raw material.

Compatibility between inorganic BF and organic PLA is an issue to address since it determines their composites' performance. In an attempt to obtain improved mechanical properties of the BF/PLA composites, this preliminary study examines various compatibilizing methods reportedly used for treating glass fibers [1-3]. The chemical and physical treatments include silane treatment, atmospheric plasma polymerization, and the use of maleic anhydride coupling agent. In addition, the effect of size removal from basalt fiber is also observed.

2 Experimental

PLA films used were from Green Chemical Co., Ltd., Korea. Basalt fiber was supplied in the form of woven fabric by YJC Co., Ltd., Korea.

The silane treatment on basalt fiber use γ -glycidoxypropyltrimethoxysilane (GPS) solution (the GPS was of Dow Corning/Xiameter), formulated according to recommended industrial practice for treating glass

fiber. The selection of GPS is based on our previous works on composites with PLA matrix which found that GPS solution treated fibers resulted composites better mechanical properties than composites whose fiber was treated with other types of silane [4]. The BF was immersed for either 15 minutes or one hour in the GPS solution.

Plasma polymerization was conducted on in house atmospheric glow discharge (AGD) plasma system (Fig. 1). Glow is generated at atmospheric pressure at or near ambient temperature, enabling continuous process without the need for vacuum system. To generate the glow, 3 kV AC power supply and radio frequency source at 20 kHz were used. The precursor for plasma polymerization was acrylic acid monomer, with helium as the carrier gas. The acrylic acid monomer used was of reagent grade, procured from Junsei Chemicals. The setting to generate the atmospheric glow corresponded to our prior experience where plasma polymer of acrylic acid was able to adhere onto the treated fibers [4]. The basalt fiber was exposed to AGD plasma for 0.5, 1.5, 3, and 4.5 minutes.

Fig. 1. Schematic of the atmospheric glow discharge plasma system [4].

MAPLA was prepared by extruding blends of MA, dicumyl peroxide, and PLA (300:10.5:3000) [2]. MA and dicumyl peroxide were supplied by Sigma Aldrich. Subsequently, PLA film containing 10 wt%

MAPLA was made by solution casting of the MAPLA pellets using chloroform solvent [2].

Desizing for the basalt fiber was done by furnace heating at 450°C for 90 minutes.

PLA films and treated BF were hot pressed to produce composites with 25 wt% BF content. For comparisons, neat PLA and untreated BF/PLA composite (control) were also fabricated.

Tensile test were conducted on the composites according to ASTM D3039. Selected samples were further characterized using digital scanning calorimeter (DSC), Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), and scanning electron microscope (SEM).

3 Results and Discussion

Initial assessment on silane treated BF/PLA composite reveals short immersion time was better than the recommended longer time (Table 1). For the particular silane treatments, longer immersion time led to decreasing both strength and modulus.

Table 1. Mechanical properties of silane treated BF/PLA composites.

Immersion time (min)	Tensile strength (MPa)	Modulus (GPa)
15	73.56	2.43
60	63.41	1.82

In the case of plasma polymerized BF/PLA composite, there was a trend of decline for treatment up to 1.5 minutes and rebound afterwards (Table 2). The longest exposure time (4.5 minutes) resulted composite with the highest strength and stiffness.

Table 2. Mechanical properties of plasma polymerized BF/PLA composites.

Plasma time (min)	Tensile strength (MPa)	Modulus (GPa)
0.5	48.45	1.98
1.5	39.43	1.76
3	71.48	2.32
4.5	84.71	2.78

Observation on BF surface shows different morphology of treated and as received BF (Fig. 2). The as received BF contains spots and clumps of

manufacturer's size materials (Fig. 2a), distinct when compared to the desized BF which features lean fiber surface (Fig. 2b). The distribution of size throughout fiber surface seems uneven, with large portion is uncovered while some sites are overly applied. Morphology of typical silane treated BF (Fig. 2c) showed more evenly distributed silane throughout BF surface. It was as expected, given the much longer reaction time in applying silane compared to that of during the BF processing by the manufacturer. Sites of over sizing from the manufacturer's size materials still existed. Similarly, AGD plasma polymerized BF surface (Fig. 2d) showed smoother appearance than BF as is.

Fig. 2. Morphology of basalt fibers: (a) as is, (b) desized, (c) silane treated, and (d) plasma polymerized.

The FTIR spectra of silane treated and plasma polymerized BF were compared to BF as is (pertinent bands are denoted in Table 3). Silane treated BF exhibited shift on Si—O peak. It indicated more intense silanol presence, likely due to the more silane grafted on BF surface. Also of interest is the C—O peak which shifted after silane treatment. The carbonyl bond corresponds to the organofunctional reactive group of the silane. The shift in carbonyl peak suggested that the organofunctional reactive group contained in manufacturer's silane based size [5-7] is different from the glycidoxy reactive organic group contained in GPS. The presence of ppAA on BF surface was indicated by the shift in C=O peak which represents the grafted acrylic acid [8]. The AGD plasma

polymerization was conducted on as received BF, which was sized. So, the reaction might also involve the silane and any substance of the size material. The helium used within the glow has high metastable energies ($2^3S = 19.8$ eV and $2^1S = 20.7$ eV) [9]. It was capable of dissociating C=C bond to form ppAA. It also was high enough to dissociate Si-O, Si-C, as well as C-O bonds which are related to silane size. The shifts in Si-O and C-O peaks compared to those of as received BF were the indication. Therefore, it can be deduced that acrylic acid monomers and size materials were dissociated by metastable helium radicals. These active species deposited and polymerized further to form ppAA (which might also contain Si molecules) on BF surface.

Table 3. FTIR bands of basalt fibers.

Basalt fiber type	$\nu_{C=O}$	ν_{C-O}	ν_{Si-O}
As received	1758	1277	885
Silane treated	NA**	1272	901
Plasma polymerized	1749	1251	893

*) All units in cm^{-1}

**) Not applicable

Strength and stiffness of the composites and neat PLA are plotted in Fig. 3. It is notable that untreated BF readily exhibits reinforcement effect to the composite. Desizing resulted composite with higher stiffness yet lower strength. These indicated less compatibility between desized BF with PLA matrix. Apparently, the manufacturer's proprietary size also works on thermoplastics although likely the silane-based size was formulated towards thermoset resins. The MAPLA coupling agent increased tensile strength (only slightly) yet reduced stiffness of the composite. Possible circumstances were the MA group formed linkages with both free surface of BF and silane based size on BF surface. Also, the corresponding grafted PLA copolymer chains might form two types of interphase layer, accordingly, with main PLA phase. In addition to these interphases, there could still be sized BF surface which was not penetrated by the MAPLA. Overall, combination of properties of these interphases determined the behavior of the BF/MAPLA/PLA composite.

For silane treated BF/PLA composite, the more even silane distribution on BF surface and more suitable organofunctional reactive group translated to the

higher mechanical properties of the corresponding composites compared to control.

As for the composite having plasma polymerized BF, the interphase between ppAA and PLA matrix that determines the mechanical properties of the associated composite showed tendency of reinforcement effect.

Fig. 3. Strength and stiffness of neat PLA and BF/PLA composites.

From DSC analysis (Table 4), the presence of silane reduced melting temperature and crystallinity of the composite, compared to those of untreated BF/PLA counterpart. Lean BF produced composite with lowest melting temperature and highest crystallinity while untreated BF (with silane based size) produced the opposites. These explained that the original size (of the latter) contained organic substances other than silane. Silane treated and plasma polymerized BF/PLA composites' crystallinity was less than that of neat PLA and control. Less crystallinity often means worse mechanical properties yet improved adhesion between silane and ppAA interphases and the PLA seemed offsetting it.

Table 4. Thermal properties of BF/PLA composites.

Sample	T_m	$\Delta H_f^{a)}$	Crystallinity ^{b)}
	($^{\circ}C$)	J/g	%
PLA	113.5	21.13	24.3
Control	114.3	18.35	28.1
Desized	112.5	12.81	19.6
MAPLA	112.8	13.27	20.3
Plasma polymerized	112.7	13.79	21.1
Silane treated	111.8	13.89	21.3

^{a)} Per gram of total sample

^{b)} Based on unit mass of PLA component. ΔH_f for pure PLA crystal = 87 J/g

The composites' cross section shows some gaps between PLA matrix and silane treated and plasma polymerized BF (Fig. 4), although they were in better condition than the control. It indicates there are sites with weak hydrogen bonding or van der Waals interaction between silane and ppAA interphases and PLA.

Fig. 4. Cross section of (a) silane treated and (b) plasma polymerized BF/PLA composites

In summary, for getting even better reinforcement effects, desizing was not an option (from processing and composite performance points of view). Addition of MAPLA coupling agent was still potential, yet further examination is required. Within scope of the study, improved mechanical properties of BF/PLA composites are obtainable through silane treatment and plasma polymerization. Bulk properties of the PLA/BF composites can be controlled through varying the treatment variables which in turn affecting the properties of the interphase layer between the treated BF and the PLA matrix.

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